

Machine and Deep Learning in Anti-Inflammatory Drug Discovery

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ABSTRACT

In this systematic review, the classical computer-aided methods of drug design and discovery are introduced, the process of inflammation and the common anti-inflammatories are presented and the reasons for developing new anti-inflammatory medications are discussed. In a more detailed approach in the discussion section, common machine and deep learning approaches used in modern anti-inflammatory drug design and discovery efforts are reviewed. At the end, an overview of the current state of research in machine and deep learning-assisted anti-inflammatory drug discovery is concluded and a perspective of the future landscape in this field of research is presented in the outlook section.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Computing Methodologies • Modelling and Prediction • Machine and Deep Learning

KEYWORDS

Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Anti-Inflammatory Drugs, Virtual Screening

1. Introduction

In pharmaceutical research a drug discovery endeavor is usually taken on because there is a disease or clinical condition without suitable medical products available. The initial research generates data to develop a hypothesis that the inhibition or activation of a certain protein or pathway will result in a therapeutic effect in the clinical condition. Developing this hypothesis usually takes years of research in both academia and pharmaceutical industry across multiple research groups. In the next step, the drug discovery efforts follow to discover chemical compounds that can inhibit or activate the certain protein or pathway to improve the clinical condition according to the hypothesis. The first discovered suitable initial candidate is called a lead compound. During lead discovery, an intensive search ensues to find a drug-like small molecule or biological therapeutic that improves the state of the clinical condition based on the hypothesized mechanism. The lead compound is a development candidate that will progress into

preclinical, and if successful, into clinical development and ultimately will be a marketed medicine. Having available ever-evolving medical, biological, chemical, and bioinformatical technologies at their disposal, the scientific community discovers new clinical conditions and new pathways and proteins that are involved in well-known diseases every year. This enormous volume of data and information increases the demand in pharmaceutical products market to develop new drugs with better performance and less side effects. Developing a new drug from original idea to the launch of a finished product is a complex process which can take 12–15 years and cost billions of dollars. Therefore, there is a need to come up with new strategies and techniques to make these long and expensive processes shorter and cheaper to meet the increasing demand of the market for the development of new drugs. [1-3]

1.1. Classical Computer-Aided Drug Discovery

With the ever-improving computer hardware, software, and algorithms, drug discovery and design have benefited from various computational methods which reduce the time and cost of drug development, significantly. [4, 5]

1.1.1. Molecular Simulations

These methods are based on multiscale models for complex biochemical systems. The combination of quantum mechanics and molecular mechanics or the combination of classical Newtonian mechanics and molecular dynamics can be used to study the action mechanism of certain drugs, to identify potential drug binding sites on target proteins, and the calculation of binding free energy between target proteins and drug molecules. [4, 6, 7]

1.1.2. Drug Design and Virtual Screening

1.1.2.1. Structure Based Drug Design

In this approach available structural models of the target proteins, which are provided by experimental measurements such as X-ray diffraction and nuclear magnetic resonance are used and molecular modeling is applied to analyze the physicochemical properties of drug binding sites on the receptor (electrostatic field, hydrophobic

field, hydrogen bond, and key residues). Then, the small molecule databases are searched, or a drug design technique is used to identify the suitable molecules which molecular shapes match the binding sites of the receptor and binding affinity is high. [4, 8]

1.1.2.2. *Ligand Based Drug Design*

Ligand-based drug design doesn't search small molecule libraries. Instead, it relies on the binding of known molecules to the target macromolecule. Using these known molecules, a model is developed that defines the minimum necessary structural characteristics a molecule must possess to bind to the target. Ligand-based drug design includes quantitative structure–activity relationship models (QSAR) in which a correlation between calculated properties of molecules and their experimentally determined biological activity is derived. This model can predict the activity of new analogs. [4, 9]

1.1.2.3. *Virtual Screening*

Virtual screening (VS) is an umbrella term used in drug discovery to search libraries of small molecules in order to identify the structures which are most likely to bind to a drug target. The theoretical basis is that the process of ligand and receptor recognition relies on spatial shape matching and energy matching, which is the theory of “inducing fit”. [4, 10] Virtual screening includes methods such as molecular docking (predicting interaction patterns between proteins and small molecules, to evaluate the binding between two molecules), [11, 12] pharmacophore modelling (Describing molecular features necessary for molecular recognition of a ligand by a biological target), [13, 14] and QSAR (Studying the interactions between small molecules and biological targets quantitatively). [15, 16]

1.1.3. *De Novo Drug Design*

Computer-based de novo drug design methods are mainly based on generating small molecule compounds with ideal physicochemical and pharmacological properties. The fragment-based de novo design method starts with small building blocks. The initial molecular building blocks with desired properties are either elaborated upon (growing), directly connected (joining), or connected by a linker (linking). This process can be iterated until one or more molecules with the desired properties are obtained. Multiscale de novo drug design is a novel concept that combines QSAR models, quantum mechanics calculations, and fragment-based drug discovery. [4, 17]

1.2. Anti-Inflammatory Drugs

Inflammation is a complex biological response of the body tissue to harmful stimuli such as pathogens, irritants, and damaged tissue.

This process is extremely complicated and involves multiple types of immune cells, blood vessels, and numerous molecular biomarkers and targets. While acute inflammation is usually the initial response of the body to harmful stimuli, chronic inflammation involves a progressive shift in the type of cells present at the site of inflammation and is characterized by simultaneous destruction and healing of the tissue. While inflammation is an extremely important function of the healthy human body, inflammatory abnormalities are a large group of disorders that underlie a vast variety of human diseases such as allergic reactions, myopathies, immune system disorders, cancer, atherosclerosis, and ischemic heart disease. [18, 19] Therefore, anti-inflammatory medications are prescribed to limit the negative effects of the inflammation process in these diseases. Additionally, anti-inflammatory drugs remedy pain by reducing inflammation. Anti-inflammatory drugs are divided into two main categories: 1) corticosteroids, a class of steroid hormones and their synthetic analogues that are produced in the adrenal cortex of vertebrates (*e.g.*, dexamethasone, and prednisone). [20] 2) Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) that counteract the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme, which synthesizes prostaglandins, creating inflammation (*e.g.*, aspirin, ibuprofen, and naproxen). [21]

Given the very complex nature of the inflammation processes in the body and the number of biochemical molecules involved, there likely are multiple target proteins that can be used to develop drugs to limit or inhibit inflammation and subsequently pain. This especially holds true in our era, that computer assisted methods used in bioinformatics unveil new structural and mechanistic details about the molecules involved in inflammation and their interactions, regularly. In addition, both common corticosteroid and NSAIDs have multiple side effects, intensifying the urge to invest time and effort in finding new alternative anti-inflammatory (and subsequently pain relieving) drugs. [22, 23]

2. DISCUSSION

2.1. Machine Learning (ML) Assisted Drug Design

In the process of drug discovery, ML methods have mostly been used in all the above-mentioned computational approaches and other related fields over the past few decades (Appendix A, Figure 1). With the accumulation of “big” data on the molecular structures and their properties and activities, ML methods have developed into deep learning (DL) approaches to deal with important biological properties from large compound databases. ML and DL have been used in various applications in this context such as prediction of drug–protein interactions, discovery of drug efficacy,

and ensuring the safety biomarkers (Appendix A, Figure 2). [24-28]

2.2. Machine Learning in Modern Anti-Inflammatory Drug Design and Discovery

Generally, ML-based drug discovery includes five steps: 1) target selection, 2) data collection, 3) data description, 4) model building, and 5) model evaluation. In the first step an appropriate target (usually a protein) is chosen which activity in inflammation process is already proved. If the study includes a structure-based approach, the small molecule libraries are searched for all potential structures that could inhibit or activate the target. If the ligand-based approach is followed, the similar elements in the structure of the small molecules that can inhibit or activate the target will be used as data. Afterwards, the most important step is to collect high-quality experimental data, which are obtained from specialized cheminformatic databases. Usually, two datasets including a positive dataset and a negative dataset are collected and a classification model is trained on this data. To characterize chemical structures of data as numeric features, two common description methods are utilized (molecular descriptors and molecular fingerprints). There are multiple online tools to calculate descriptors (*e.g.*, PaDel-Descriptor [29] and E-Dragon [30]). The calculated descriptors could be mathematically further manipulated (*e.g.*, Pearson correlation analysis) to improve the model [31]. After constructing the predictive models, performance metrics, including accuracy (Q), and Matthew's correlation coefficient (MCC), and area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC) are used to evaluate the performance of the models. [32]

2.2.1. Novel NSAID Discovery

In many studies the focus has been put on finding new molecular candidates, which inhibit COX but show fewer side effects than the classical NSAIDs. QSAR is one of the approaches that has been mostly used to investigate these structures. For example, a study published in 2022 involves the application of chemical descriptors and ML (22 ML classification models) to predict the bioactivity classes of molecules for COX-2 inhibition using real multidimensional COX-2 inhibitors (PubChem Fingerprints) obtained from a curated database (ChEMBL). Among all the tested algorithms, extreme gradient boosting classifier (XGB Classifier) was found to be the best performer (Q of 0.9484 and MCC of 0.8741). [33]

In some other studies a combination of approaches has been used to repurpose existing drugs for anti-inflammatory effects. For example, the interaction sites between drugs and targets were determined by molecular docking. 67 drug-target interaction

descriptors were calculated to describe the drug-target interactions, and 22 important descriptors were screened for drug classification by support vector machine (SVM), light gradient boosting method (LightGBM), and artificial neural network (ANN) (Q of 0.9329, 0.9268, and 0.9451, and MCC of 0.852, 0.840, and 0.882, respectively). Number of atom pairs, force field, and hydrophobic interactions were the key features for classifying anti-inflammatory drugs. [34]

2.2.2. Ant-inflammatory peptides (AIPs)

Although information about peptides are still scattered across the literature, several peptide-based databases exist that offer experimentally validated data [32] and are used in building predictive and design models of peptide drugs. Although these databases focus on specific type of peptides such as antimicrobial peptides and are not very comprehensive and most of them only cover the positive result of peptide activity, many of them play a crucial role in AIP discovery (*e.g.*, APD [35], Peptaibol [36], CyBase [37], DADP [38], Hemolytik [39], AVPdb [40], DBAASP [41], SATPbd [42]). ML methods such as SVM, random forests (RF), and ANN have been widely applied to develop predictive models for peptide activity. [32]

In 2017, Gupta et al. [43] developed predictive models to discriminate the AIPs from non-AIPs by utilizing SVM and RF methods (Q and MCC value of SVM model on validation set 0.72 and 0.45). The web server IL-10pred was constructed for the prediction of potential interleukin-10 (IL-10) inducing peptides, [44] which are one of the important cytokines, that suppress inflammatory responses, alleviate autoimmune pathologies [45] and extend graft survival [46]. This server was developed based on RF algorithm by utilizing dipeptide composition, which displayed the highest Q and MCC value of 0.8224 and 0.59. AIP-Pred [47] is a web server, which focuses on identifying potential AIP candidates using extremely randomized tree (ERT), SVM, k-nearest neighbor (kNN) and RF approaches combined with the selected optimal features to build classifiers. The AUC value of the best classifier achieved 0.814 on an independent dataset. Apart from the databases and online predictive tools, there are many ML-based in silico studies for predicting peptide activity that are not integrated to web servers. For example, AntiFlamPred uses a deep neural network (DNN) approach to predict the anti-inflammatory response of peptides with an AUC of 0.919 and MCC of 0.735. [48]

2.2.3. Anti-inflammatory plant-based compounds and natural products

Usually, compounds obtained from natural sources have little or no side effects, thus searching for new lead compounds among

traditionally used anti-inflammatory medications is a common strategy. Therefore, high throughput in silico ML screening methods to identify potential compounds from natural sources is a growing field in drug discovery efforts. In addition to COX, lipoxygenase pathway is important in inflammatory processes; therefore, natural inhibitors of both pathways would act as high efficacy and low side effect anti-inflammatory medications. In one of the early studies with this metabolomic approach, leaf extracts of Asteraceae species with in vitro dual inhibition of cyclooxygenase-1 and 5-lipoxygenase were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography and high-resolution mass spectrometry analysis using ML algorithms. As a result, a robust ANN model for predicting the anti-inflammatory activity of natural compounds was obtained (Q of 0.81). [49-51] This approach has been used by multiple other studies to inhibit the activity of inflammatory biomarkers. [52-55]

In another study, three ML approaches, including SVM, RF and GBM have been applied to develop the classification model. The model was generated using the cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitors reported in the ChEMBL database (Q of SVM, RF and GBM was found to be 0.7540, 0.7479, and 0.7460, respectively). Application of the model on NuBBE database, a repository of natural compounds, led the researchers to identify a natural compound, enhydrin, possessing analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities. [56] Recently, a comprehensive online web platform (InflamNat) has been developed for anti-inflammatory natural product research. InflamNat is a database containing the physicochemical properties, cellular anti-inflammatory bioactivities, and molecular targets of 1351 natural products that tested on their anti-inflammatory activities. It also provides two ML-based predictive tools specifically designed for natural products that (1) predict the anti-inflammatory activity of natural products and (2) predict the compound-target relationship for compounds and targets collected in the database but lacking existing relationship data. A novel multi-tokenization transformer model was used as the sequential encoder for both predictive tools (AUC of 0.842 and 0.872 in anti-inflammatory activity prediction and compound-target interactions, respectively). [57]

3. CONCLUSION

The process of designing and developing new drugs including anti-inflammatory drugs is extremely expensive and cumbersome. However, currently available anti-inflammatory medications (corticosteroids and NSAIDs) have severe side effects. Additionally, the new advancements in computational biology, cheminformatics, and bioinformatics, unveil the molecular

mechanisms behind inflammation with a speed we have never experienced in science before. Scientists have used this opportunity to apply ML assisted methods towards the anti-inflammatory drug design and discovery (structure-based and ligand-based approaches). These efforts have been taken in three directions: 1) ML assisted discovery of novel NSAIDs with less side effects, 2) ML assisted discovery of AIPs with high specificity, 3) ML assisted discovery of anti-inflammatory natural products with no side effects. Generally, the best results are the product of merging some of the classical approaches in drug design and discovery (e.g., docking and QSAR) with the state-of-the-art ML and DL methods.

4. OUTLOOK

The urge to develop new anti-inflammatory drugs with less or no side effects, the availability of enormous amount of data on molecular mechanisms of inflammation, and the availability of cheap and easy computational approaches lead the direction of future anti-inflammatory drug design and development to the combination of classical methods (molecular docking, simulation, QSAR) and best performing ML and DL algorithms in data science. It is difficult to imagine the future of anti-inflammatory drug development without the involvement of ML and DL methods. However, the need for comprehensive and well curated databases for biomarkers, targets, and small molecules including accurate and exhaustive data is a challenge that should be addressed by the scientific community in order to facilitate the future ML-assisted drug design and discovery endeavors.

REFERENCES

1. Hughes, J.P., et al., *Principles of early drug discovery*. British journal of pharmacology, 2011. **162**(6): p. 1239-1249.
2. Atanasov, A.G., et al., *Natural products in drug discovery: advances and opportunities*. Nature reviews Drug discovery, 2021. **20**(3): p. 200-216.
3. Muttenthaler, M., et al., *Trends in peptide drug discovery*. Nature reviews Drug discovery, 2021. **20**(4): p. 309-325.
4. Lin, X., X. Li, and X. Lin, *A review on applications of computational methods in drug screening and design*. Molecules, 2020. **25**(6): p. 1375.
5. Willems, H., S. De Cesco, and F. Svensson, *Computational Chemistry on a Budget: Supporting Drug Discovery with Limited Resources: Miniperspective*. Journal of Medicinal Chemistry, 2020. **63**(18): p. 10158-10169.
6. Decherchi, S. and A. Cavalli, *Thermodynamics and kinetics of drug-target binding by molecular simulation*. Chemical Reviews, 2020. **120**(23): p. 12788-12833.
7. Nunes-Alves, A., D.B. Kokh, and R.C. Wade, *Recent progress in molecular simulation methods for drug*

- binding kinetics*. Current Opinion in Structural Biology, 2020. **64**: p. 126-133.
8. Maia, E.H.B., et al., *Structure-based virtual screening: from classical to artificial intelligence*. Frontiers in chemistry, 2020. **8**: p. 343.
 9. Garcia-Hernandez, C., A. Fernandez, and F. Serratos, *Ligand-based virtual screening using graph edit distance as molecular similarity measure*. Journal of chemical information and modeling, 2019. **59**(4): p. 1410-1421.
 10. da Silva Rocha, S.F., et al., *Virtual screening techniques in drug discovery: review and recent applications*. Current topics in medicinal chemistry, 2019. **19**(19): p. 1751-1767.
 11. Sethi, A., et al., *Molecular docking in modern drug discovery: Principles and recent applications*. Drug discovery and development-new advances, 2019. **2**: p. 1-21.
 12. Pinzi, L. and G. Rastelli, *Molecular docking: shifting paradigms in drug discovery*. International journal of molecular sciences, 2019. **20**(18): p. 4331.
 13. Sun, H., *Pharmacophore-based virtual screening*. Current medicinal chemistry, 2008. **15**(10): p. 1018-1024.
 14. Caporuscio, F. and A. Tafi, *Pharmacophore modelling: a forty year old approach and its modern synergies*. Current medicinal chemistry, 2011. **18**(17): p. 2543-2553.
 15. Muratov, E.N., et al., *QSAR without borders*. Chemical Society Reviews, 2020. **49**(11): p. 3525-3564.
 16. Neves, B.J., et al., *QSAR-based virtual screening: advances and applications in drug discovery*. Frontiers in pharmacology, 2018. **9**: p. 1275.
 17. Hartenfeller, M. and G. Schneider, *De novo drug design*. Chemoinformatics and computational chemical biology, 2010: p. 299-323.
 18. Nathan, C. and A. Ding, *Nonresolving inflammation*. Cell, 2010. **140**(6): p. 871-882.
 19. Okin, D. and R. Medzhitov, *Evolution of inflammatory diseases*. Current Biology, 2012. **22**(17): p. R733-R740.
 20. Kapugi, M. and K. Cunningham, *Corticosteroids*. Orthopaedic Nursing, 2019. **38**(5): p. 336-339.
 21. Brune, K. and P. Patrignani, *New insights into the use of currently available non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs*. Journal of pain research, 2015. **8**: p. 105.
 22. Buchman, A.L., *Side effects of corticosteroid therapy*. Journal of clinical gastroenterology, 2001. **33**(4): p. 289-294.
 23. Scheiman, J.M., *NSAID-induced gastrointestinal injury*. Journal of clinical gastroenterology, 2016. **50**(1): p. 5-10.
 24. Dara, S., et al., *Machine learning in drug discovery: a review*. Artificial Intelligence Review, 2022. **55**(3): p. 1947-1999.
 25. Smith, J.S., A.E. Roitberg, and O. Isayev, *Transforming computational drug discovery with machine learning and AI*. 2018, ACS Publications. p. 1065-1069.
 26. Bender, A. and I. Cortés-Ciriano, *Artificial intelligence in drug discovery: what is realistic, what are illusions? Part I: ways to make an impact, and why we are not there yet*. Drug discovery today, 2021. **26**(2): p. 511-524.
 27. Bender, A. and I. Cortes-Ciriano, *Artificial intelligence in drug discovery: what is realistic, what are illusions? Part 2: a discussion of chemical and biological data*. Drug Discovery Today, 2021. **26**(4): p. 1040-1052.
 28. Ghasemi, F., et al., *Neural network and deep-learning algorithms used in QSAR studies: merits and drawbacks*. Drug discovery today, 2018. **23**(10): p. 1784-1790.
 29. Yap, C.W., *PaDEL-descriptor: An open source software to calculate molecular descriptors and fingerprints*. Journal of computational chemistry, 2011. **32**(7): p. 1466-1474.
 30. Tetko, I.V., et al., *Virtual computational chemistry laboratory—design and description*. Journal of computer-aided molecular design, 2005. **19**(6): p. 453-463.
 31. Fang, J., et al., *Discovery of neuroprotective compounds by machine learning approaches*. RSC advances, 2016. **6**(12): p. 9857-9871.
 32. Wu, Q., et al., *Recent progress in machine learning-based prediction of peptide activity for drug discovery*. Current topics in medicinal chemistry, 2019. **19**(1): p. 4-16.
 33. Dibia, K.T., et al., *Exploration of the quantitative Structure-Activity relationships for predicting Cyclooxygenase-2 inhibition bioactivity by Machine learning approaches*. Results in Chemistry, 2022. **4**: p. 100272.
 34. Huang, S. and Y. Ding, *Identification of Anticancer and Anti-inflammatory Drugs from Drugtarget Interaction Descriptors by Machine Learning*. Letters in Drug Design & Discovery, 2022. **19**(9): p. 800-810.
 35. tool, O., *APD*.
 36. *Peptaibol*. <http://peptaibol.cryst.bbk.ac.uk/home.shtml>
 37. *CyBase*. <https://www.cybase.org.au/>
 38. *DADP*. <http://split4.pmfst.hr/dadp/>
 39. *Hemolytik*. <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/42/D1/D444/1041683>
 40. *AVPdb*. <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/42/D1/D1147/1058993>
 41. *DBAASP*. <https://dbaasp.org/>
 42. *SATPdb*. <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/44/D1/D1119/2502618>
 43. Gupta, S., et al., *Prediction of anti-inflammatory proteins/peptides: an insilico approach*. Journal of translational medicine, 2017. **15**(1): p. 1-11.
 44. Nagpal, G., et al., *Computer-aided designing of immunosuppressive peptides based on IL-10 inducing potential*. Scientific reports, 2017. **7**(1): p. 1-10.
 45. Hawrylowicz, C. and A. O'garra, *Potential role of interleukin-10-secreting regulatory T cells in allergy and asthma*. Nature Reviews Immunology, 2005. **5**(4): p. 271-283.
 46. Bromberg, J.S., *IL-10 immunosuppression in transplantation*. Current opinion in immunology, 1995. **7**(5): p. 639-643.
 47. Manavalan, B., et al., *AIPpred: sequence-based prediction of anti-inflammatory peptides using random forest*. Frontiers in pharmacology, 2018. **9**: p. 276.
 48. Alotaibi, F., M. Attique, and Y.D. Khan, *AntiFlamPred: an anti-inflammatory peptide predictor for drug*

- selection strategies*. Comput Mater Contin, 2021. **69**: p. 1039-1055.
49. Chagas-Paula, D., et al., *Discovery of plant anti-inflammatory biomarkers by machine learning algorithms and metabolomic studies*. Planta Medica, 2013. **79**(13): p. SL27.
50. Chagas-Paula, D.A., et al., *Prediction of anti-inflammatory plants and discovery of their biomarkers by machine learning algorithms and metabolomic studies*. Planta Medica, 2015. **81**(06): p. 450-458.
51. Chagas-Paula, D.A., et al., *A metabolomic approach to target compounds from the Asteraceae family for dual COX and LOX inhibition*. Metabolites, 2015. **5**(3): p. 404-430.
52. Usman, A.G., et al., *The effect of ethanolic leaves extract of Hymenodictyon floribundum on inflammatory biomarkers: a data-driven approach*. Bulletin of the National Research Centre, 2021. **45**(1): p. 1-12.
53. Nicacio, K.d.J., et al., *Anti-Inflammatory Markers of Hops Cultivars (Humulus lupulus L.) Evaluated by Untargeted Metabolomics Strategy*. Chemistry & Biodiversity, 2022. **19**(4): p. e202100966.
54. Ferreira, M.S., et al., *Systematic Review of Anti-inflammatory Agents from Aspergillus Species*. Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia, 2021: p. 1-12.
55. Domingos, O.d.S., et al., *Anti-inflammatory derivatives with dual mechanism of action from the metabolomic screening of Poincianella pluviosa*. Molecules, 2019. **24**(23): p. 4375.
56. Khan, M.F., R.B. Rashid, and M.A. Rashid, *Identification of Natural Compounds with Analgesic and Antiinflammatory Properties Using Machine Learning and Molecular Docking Studies*. Letters in Drug Design & Discovery, 2022. **19**(3): p. 256-262.
57. Zhang, R., et al., *InflamNat: web-based database and predictor of anti-inflammatory natural products*. Journal of Cheminformatics, 2022. **14**(1): p. 1-11.

A APPENDICES

A.1 Figures

Figure 1. Different areas of the application of the ML techniques in drug discovery and development. [24]

Figure 2. ML mechanisms used in drug discovery and design. [24]